

Deliverable D4.1 Report on the recommended ontologies for preclinical image datasets and technologies

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

OLS	Ontology Look-up System
EBI	European Bioinformatics Institute
UMLS	Unified Medical Language System
OBO	Open Biomedical Ontologies
DOID	Human Disease Ontology
MONDO	Mondo Disease Ontology
CHEBI	Chemical Entities of Biological Interest
FMA	Foundational Model of Anatomy Ontology
MA	Mouse adult gross anatomy
AEO	Anatomical Entity Ontology
UBERON	Uber Anatomy Ontology
CL	Cell Ontology
CLO	Cell Line Ontology
GO	Gene Ontology
SO	Sequence types and features ontology
BIM	Biomedical Image Ontology
OBI	Ontology for Biomedical Investigations
XCO	Experimental conditions ontology
CMO	Clinical Measurement Ontology
MMO	Measurement method ontology
OBSC	Ontology of Biological and Clinical Statistics
MPATH	Mouse Pathology Ontology
PATHLEX	Anatomic Pathology Lexicon
MP	Mammalian Phenotype Ontology
HPO	Human Phenotype Ontology

RADLEX	Radiology Lexicon
ROO	Radiation Oncology Ontology
SWO	Software Ontology
RO	Radiomics Ontology
EFO	Experimental Factor Ontology
RS	Rat Strain Ontology
SNOMED CT	Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine Clinical Terms
NCIT	Thesaurus del National Cancer Institute

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Executive Summary

Preclinical imaging has emerged over the past two decades as a rapidly expanding field, playing a fundamental role in both basic research and the development of new therapies. The advent of new imaging modalities and increasingly sensitive and specific probes allow us to obtain in vivo information at the anatomical, molecular and functional levels. This exponential increase in the ability to generate image datasets has not gone hand in hand with the ability to make these datasets findable and reusable. One of the main limitations is related to the lack of a set of ontologies large enough to cover the multidisciplinary nature of preclinical imaging. The aim of this deliverable is to identify the different domains in which preclinical images fall, to search and evaluate the different ontologies that can cover each of the various domains and to select the more useful ontologies based on a series of criteria. The final objective is to provide a set of recommended ontologies for improving the findability of preclinical image datasets.

1. Introduction

Preclinical imaging encompasses several domains, being natively multi-disciplinary with a fundamental role in basic science, drug development and translation. In the last decades the amount of information that preclinical images can provide has dramatically expanded, from anatomical to functional to molecular ones, paralleled to the volume of preclinical images produced on a daily basis by preclinical imaging centers worldwide. Unfortunately, most of the acquired preclinical image datasets are not easily findable because of the lack of dedicated repositories and these images are not interoperable because of the lack of ontologies associated to the metadata describing these images. As a consequence, the preclinical imaging field is far from an acceptable level of FAIRness of the data that are produced by this field. To overcome this limitation, a landscape analysis of existing ontologies for the preclinical imaging field is an urgent need for improving the FAIRification of the preclinical image datasets. Ontologies provide a well-defined vocabulary for precise, machine-readable description of knowledge about a given domain that are increasingly used to facilitate information processing in biomedical research and health care systems, where managing the increasing flow of biomedical data is a significant challenge [1].

Here we present a systematic analysis of the multidisciplinary domains that are associated with the field of preclinical imaging combined with a landscape analysis to identify, characterize and evaluate all the potential associated ontologies, i.e. controlled vocabularies that describe the meaning of the data that are available for each identified domain. The set of recommended ontologies that will be provided will be essential for enhancing data interoperability, integration and analysis of preclinical image datasets across various domains and platforms [2].

2. Identification of domains and its ontologies

A detailed description of the identification of domains and associated ontologies, as well as on the evaluation of the identified ontologies is provided in deliverable [D2.1](#).

Briefly, 14 domains were identified to cover the multiple disciplines of preclinical imaging datasets and 35 ontologies were selected to cover all the domains, with at least two ontologies for each domain. Additionally, the DUO (data use condition) ontology was also included (but not scored) for making datasets discoverable based on the intended secondary usage or for any restriction for reuse. For each ontology, the following information (or criteria) was collected: file formats, number of terms, type of licence, accessibility to the ontology, the date of the last update, number of citations and species coverage and reported in a tabular format in Deliverable 2.1 - [W Ontology_landscape_analysis_preclinical_imaging.docx](#).

3. Selection and scoring criteria for ontologies

Since more than one ontology was identified that could be associated to each domain, we opt for a scoring criteria for the selection of the ontology that should be recommended for a specific domain. The selected ontology will provide a standardised way of representing the knowledge contained in

preclinical image datasets, facilitating machine understanding and processing of the information within each domain.

3.1 Definition of scoring criteria

Firstly, the following metrics were considered to be evaluated for each ontology:

- A. Number of terms / classes
- B. Number of normalized citations
- C. Version of last update
- D. Type of licence
- E. Number of file formats
- F. Type of organism (ontology for mouse, human, all organisms)

Secondly, a score was assigned to each metric (from 0 to 3) according to distribution of the values for each metric:

- A. Number of terms / classes:
 - if $x > 60.000 \Rightarrow 3$ points
 - if $x > 10.000 \Rightarrow 2$ points
 - if $x > 1.000 \Rightarrow 1$ point
 - if $x < 1.000 \Rightarrow 0$ points

B. Number of normalized citations that was calculated by considering the number of citations of original ontology paper obtained from Pubmed, divided for the difference in years since the first publication

- if $x > 25 \Rightarrow 3$ points
- if $x > 6 \Rightarrow 2$ points
- if $x > 2 \Rightarrow 1$ point
- if $x < 2 \Rightarrow 0$ points

C. Version of last update:

- if last update < 3 months $\Rightarrow 3$ points
- if last update < 6 months $\Rightarrow 2$ points
- if last update < 1 year $\Rightarrow 1$ point
- if last update > 1 year $\Rightarrow 0$ point

D. Type of licence:

- If x = public domain =>3 points
- if x = open access (some rights reserved) =>2 points
- if x = with consortium, special license => 1 point
- If x = no public, no license => 0 points

E. Number of file formats:

- if number of formats = 4 => 3 points
- if number of formats = 3 => 2 points
- if number of formats = 2 => 1 point
- if number of formats = 1 => 0 points

F. Type of organism (ontology for mouse, human, all organisms):

- If x = ontology for all organism (human, mouse, plants) =>3 points
- if x = ontology for mouse/human =>2 points
- if x = ontology for mouse => 1 point
- if x = ontology for human => 0 points

The calculated total total score will be obtained by the sum of the score calculated for each criteria:

$$\text{Total Score} = \text{score A} + \text{score B} + \text{score C} + \text{score D} + \text{score E} + \text{score F}$$

3.2 Results of the landscape analysis

For each ontology the scoring criteria were applied to each metric and a cumulative score was obtained from the evaluation of six different metrics. Overall, most of the ontologies showed high scores in all the selected metrics, with half of the ontologies having a total score above 12. Few of them showed an overall score below 8, or were not able to achieve a score (i.e. 0 point) in some of the considered metrics. An overall view of the scoring values for each ontology and each domain is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Distribution of the overall score for each ontology belonging to the different identified domains. The score obtained for each considered metrics is shown with different colours.

3.3 Recommended ontologies

Finally, within each identified domain, the ontology with the highest score was selected and considered to be recommended for covering this domain. Of note, the recommendation is not based only on the coverage capability of a specific ontology, for which some ontologies could be better than the recommended ones, but taking into account several aspects that should facilitate the usability, the maintenance in the next years of the ontology itself and the current adoption of the selected ontology.

- DOID for Disease
- ChEBI for Drugs
- UBERON for Anatomy

- CL for Cell line
- GO for Genomic
- DICOM for imaging
- EFO for Strain
- OBI for Experimental conditions
- CMO for Biomedical and biological resource
- MPATH for Pathology
- SWO for Analysis
- RADLEX for Radiology
- MP for Phenotype
- DUO for usability

Additionally, positive feedback received by several imaging centers, including partners of the FoundingGIDE project and for reaching a wider consensus from Euro-BioImaging nodes, as well as from imaging centers of the ESMI society with a dedicated session at the European Meeting in Molecular Imaging (EMIM), allowed to consider the list as exhaustive inherently to the identified domains. Moreover, additional databases storing PIDs related to funding agencies (Open Funder Registry, <https://www.crossref.org/services/funder-registry/>), to Research Institution registry (ROR, <https://ror.org/>) and to researchers (ORCID, <https://orcid.org/>) were also included among the recommended ones, for providing useful references to further improve the findability of the associated preclinical image datasets and the connections with other repositories.

4. Conclusion

We identified several domains and evaluated different ontologies to cover the multidisciplinary domain of the preclinical imaging field with the aim of providing a set of recommended ontologies for improving the findability of preclinical image datasets. The selected set of ontologies are considered useful for describing the variety and multi-domain information contained in biomedical preclinical images, thus improving the implementation of the FAIR principles [3]. This family of recommended ontologies will facilitate the sharing and the interoperability of preclinical images with other existing repositories in the life sciences domain.

4. References

- [1] Bogumil M. Konopka; Biomedical ontologies- a review, *Biocybern. Biomed. Eng.*, 2015, 35:75-86.
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